

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D6.4 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Yearly report (2)

Funded by
the European Union

Horizon Europe research and innovation programme
project number 101059425

Funded by the European Union under grant agreement of the project 101059425. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DELIVERABLE ID

Deliverable No.	D6.4	Work Package No.	WP6	Task/s No.	T6.2, T6.3, T6.4
Work Package Title	POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS AND ADVOCACY. DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION				
Linked Task/s Title	T6.2. COMMUNICATION PLAN AND PUBLIC OUTREACH ACTIVITIES T6.3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES T6.4. EXPLOITATION PLAN AND IPR MANAGEMENT				
Dissemination level	PU	<i>(PU-Public, SEN-Sensitive)</i>			
Due date deliverable	2024-09-30	Submission date	2024-09-30		
Deliverable name	DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EXPLOITATION TEARLY REPORTS (2)				

DOCUMENT CONTRIBUTORS

Deliverable responsible	POLO	
Contributors	Organisation	
STEFANO COBELLO	POLO	
DIEGO GRAZIOLI	POLO	
MARÍA VARA BONMATÍ	ZIC	
Reviewers	Organisation	
ÁNGELA ORDÓÑEZ-CARABAÑO	COM	
CAROLINA SIMÓN	ZIC	
OLATZ MIRANDA	ZIC	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Comments
0.1	2024-07-21	First Draft
0.2	2024-09-13	Integration of partners' contributions
0.3	2024-09-26	Integration of the exploitation report
1.0	2024-09-30	Final Version

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive summary.....	6
1. Introduction.....	7
1.1 Support to the communication and dissemination efforts.....	8
2. Results of the communication activities	8
2.1 Awareness.....	8
2.1.1 LET'S CARE website	9
2.1.2 LET'S CARE social network	10
2.1.3 Potential readers.....	10
2.1.4 Online communication.....	11
2.2 Information	12
2.2.1 Contexts of implementation	12
2.2.2 Target groups	14
2.2.3 Geographical level.....	15
3. Results of the dissemination activities	16
3.1 Knowledge.....	16
3.1.1 Dissemination Contexts	16
3.1.2 Target groups	17
3.1.3 Geographical level.....	18
4. Results of Exploitation.....	19
4.1 Identification of Key Results.....	19
4.1.1 Gathering information on identified key results	19
4.1.2 Analysis of key results potential for exploitation	22
4.2 Evaluation of Key Ideas	24
4.3 Future Activities	24

5. Conclusions.....	25
Annex 1 – Communication Material.....	27
Annex 2 – List of the web links with Let’s care references	32
Annex 3 – Results of the communication activities - Awareness.....	35
Annex 4 – Results of the communication activities – Information	36
Annex 5 – Participation in conferences.....	40
Annex 6 – Results of the dissemination activities - Knowledge	54

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PAR	Participatory Action Research
RKA	Analysis of Key Results (potential for exploitation)
KERs	Key Exploitation Results

Executive summary

The second dissemination and communication report present and analyses the activities implemented by the Consortium to promote LET'S CARE objectives and approach to the main target groups from the 1st of October 2023 to the 31st of August 2024, with a comparison with the data of the first reporting period. This report analyses different levels of engagement of target groups considering the quantitative impact, the geographical level addressed, and the kind of activities implemented.

In the second year of the project, there have been 268 communication and dissemination activities, with an increase of 111 activities compared to year 1.

The **communication** activities have registered:

- 2,857 visitors to the project's website.
- 165,536 views of the media articles related to the project.
- 66,775 people were reached by mailing lists.
- 6,253 persons were reached through the project and partners' social media
- 2,949 participants in 23 conferences.
- 695 persons were involved in 30 information meetings.
- 3,661 participants in other events and collaboration with the scientific community or other EU-funded projects.

The **dissemination** activities concerning training events have involved a total of 19,346 participants.

The **exploitation** of the project's results is still at an early stage, but it has been possible to identify two elements with a potentially significant social value: PAR and Photovoice methodologies.

The document presents the results of the quantitative data collection and analysis of the results in 5 sections. The introduction describes the material produced, the methodology and the levels of engagement considered. Then, there are 2 sections about the results of the communication and dissemination activities, graphics and detailed tables on these data are reported as annexes. The fourth section presents the processes of the analysis of the exploitable results. The last section draws conclusions from the data collected.

1. Introduction

During the second year of LET'S CARE the flourishing stage has started. The communication and dissemination have focused on involving the stakeholders (especially teachers and principals) in the project's activities, sharing research outputs with key groups and improving the stakeholders' engagement to secure the long-term success of the project.

The project's second year saw a continuation of the communication and dissemination efforts initiated in the first year. Building upon the established foundation, we sought to further engage stakeholders and promote the project's potential for educational innovation. Training courses aligned with the project's core values provided opportunities for teachers and other stakeholders to actively participate in the Community of Schools, the LET'S CARE Network, and related initiatives. Through expert-led training sessions, participants gained insights into innovative teaching methodologies and strategies. These activities fostered a deeper understanding of the project's approach and potential to impact learners' well-being and educational outcomes positively.

This second dissemination and communication report of the LET'S CARE project is based on the activities undertaken by the Consortium **from September 2023 (M12) to August 2024 (M23)**¹. This analysis covers qualitative and quantitative perspectives by considering the type of activities, the geographical impact, and the number of persons reached or involved.

Each partner has been responsible for implementing communication and dissemination activities and reporting them on a shared spreadsheet², collecting the primary information necessary for the impact analysis, such as: type of activity, date and description of the activity developed, location, geographical level addressed, context, number of people reached or involved for each target group. This document also includes a description of the exploitation process in this first phase of the project, starting **from September 2023 (M12) to September 2024 (M24)**. The Consortium has collaborated to monitor the exploitable results and has begun planning actions to ensure the successful completion of this process. Although LET'S CARE is still in its early stages and the results are not yet fully developed, the PAR and Photovoice techniques, as well as the development of the LET'S CARE Hub platform subsystem, particularly with the integration of the Le Sphinx tool for data collection, have all been identified as having significant potential for social impact.

¹ Since the document had to be submitted on M24 it has not been possible to collect and analyse the data of September 2024 (M24). The activities implemented during this month will be included in the D6.5.

² The progressive reporting table of the partners is available at this link: <https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/f/5634160>

1.1 Support to the communication and dissemination efforts

During the second year of the project POLO, as WP6 leader, improved the support provided to the partners in the implementation of the communication and dissemination activities.

Regular monthly organisational meetings with representatives from each partner have been set up since M18, with one representative for each beneficiary. To further guide the partners in the implementation of the dissemination activities and their reporting, POLO has developed a [Handbook of Communication and Dissemination Practices](#).

The production of different materials has supported the communication activities:

- 1 Video
- 3 Newsletters (translated into 6 languages and shared by the partners)
- Communication materials to promote the Network of Stakeholders
- Communication material for the first LET'S CARE conference

In Annex 1, it is possible to find examples of the graphic materials and direct links to download them. The graphic materials have been produced using the Canva online service, so the partners have been able to translate and adapt them to their dissemination context easily.

The co-creation process for the communication materials has been kept in the second year of the project: POLO has cooperated with teachers and school directors to develop material that would be clear and attractive for the target groups.

2. Results of the communication activities

2.1 Awareness

To classify the activities of communication and dissemination, different levels or categories of engagement of the target groups have been considered (see D6.2). The awareness level seeks to inform the general public about the project's key topics and initiatives. While this level engages recipients less directly, it is essential for laying the groundwork for future, more participatory stages. The Consortium's communication efforts have successfully reached a broad audience. Partners have shared project information through articles and various media outlets at both local and national levels.

The main communication contexts considered in this quantitative analysis are:

- Online communication:
 - LET'S CARE website and social network.
 - Partner's media articles about the project's aims and activities.

- Partners' social media.
- Mailing lists, newsletters.
- Potential views on:
 - Online newspapers.
 - Website homepages or general articles.

The main contents communicated through these media are:

- Information about the project, objectives and description.
- Events related to the project.
- Aims of the project.
- Contents of the project.
- Activities undertaken and future activities.

2.1.1 **LET'S CARE website**

The Consortium has decided to unify the web site and the hub starting from July 2024, following the suggestions of the Project Officer after the first project's review. The web address has been maintained (www.letscaresproject.eu), and from the home page, it is possible to access the general website and LET'S CARE hub.

Figure 1. New homepage of www.letscaresproject.eu

The home page has a general presentation of the project and its main aims, a space for the latest news and other promotional materials. POLO and FHV have cooperated for the smooth integration of the two platforms.

The graphical appearance has been reviewed and uniformed. The contents have been enriched with articles and events.

The website analytics for the unified website are the following:

- 2,857 visitors.
- 20,065 views.

Figure 2. Web analytics from WPStatistics

2.1.2 LET'S CARE social network

All the articles posted on the LET'S CARE websites and the main information about the project and activities are regularly shared on the main social network:

- **Instagram** (@letscare_horizon_europe): 41 followers, 87 interactions, 92 visits
- **Facebook** (@Let's Care Horizon Project): 63 followers, 67 interactions, 728 visits
- **LinkedIn** (@Let's Care (Horizon Europe) project): 179 followers, 139 links, 4218 impressions, 666 members reached
- **X** (@LetsCareProject): 28 followers, 723 impressions

2.1.3 Potential readers

The partners have published information about the project on their own website or in others that usually have a high number of visitors. In most cases, they do not have access to the exact number of visitors to those pages. As described in the previous report, POLO has direct access to the number of visitors to its articles. LET'S CARE references have been included on the home page (<https://www.europole.org/> 6.985.147 visitors).

Furthermore, POLO has organized a conference presenting the Safe teaching approach through educational strategies and methodologies. The event “Una scuola a misura dei bambini - A children-friendly school” was held in Verona on the 26th of April 2024. It has been organized a communication campaign on the mass media: newspapers and webpages at local (such as L’Arena, VeronaNews), regional (such as RaiNews Veneto...) and national (such as INDIRE, tecnica della scuola, ADNKronos,...) level. Identifying the exact number of people reached by these communication activities has not been possible since these data are not public or available. The number of followers and the media kits provided have been considered to calculate the potential audience: about 1231000 persons.

2.1.4 Online communication

Partners have actively sought to inform the general public about the project by publishing articles on their websites and social media platforms. LET’S CARE has been presented in dedicated posts and incorporated into articles discussing related topics. In quantitative terms, this means of communication has reached a high number of target groups who are now aware of the project’s existence, even if not all the viewers have requested more information about the project.

Mailing lists have been utilized to distribute project updates, opportunities, and other relevant information, particularly to teachers. Internal databases have also been employed to share project details and track the number of individuals reached. This targeted approach has allowed for disseminating more in-depth information to specific stakeholders.

The number of people reached by each type of communication is as follows:

Table 1. Comparison and total of online communication activities

	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	TOTAL
Media articles	69,163	165,536	234,699
Social media	3,448	1158	4,606
Mailing lists	85,768	66,775	152,543
Promotional videos	9	232	241
TOTAL	158,388	233,701	392,089

The comparison of the data shows a reduction of communication through social media and mailing lists. The announcement of the launch of the project in the first year increased the number of posts on websites and social media, and in the second year, decline in the activities published online or the number of addresses of mailing lists.

It's worth mentioning that not all the partners have access to the analytics of the visitors of their official website, so this aspect distorts the number of media articles and social media impact.

The list of links to web pages, media articles, and posts on social networks can be found in Annex 2. A table with the detailed numbers of each partner can be found in Annex 3 (Table 10).

2.2 Information

The activities considered under the "Information" category aim to raise interest among the target groups and provide direct access to the project contents. These events have represented a valuable way to expand the network of stakeholders and enhance understanding of LET'S CARE's goals and content, thereby contributing to the project's overall objectives. Participants in these information events have demonstrated a keen interest in the project and its initiatives.

Comparing the results with the previous report, in the second year, the partners have doubled the implemented activities in this category of events, reaching a higher number of representatives of the target groups.

The analysis of the data collected from the participation in the information events has considered:

- Contexts of implementation of the activity (Conferences, Information Meetings, Events, Scientific cooperation, Collaboration with EU-funded projects).
- Target groups (Students, Students' Families, Education Scientific Community, Teachers, Schools, Policy Makers & Authorities, European Policy Makers, NGOs & Advocacy Organizations, General Public, and Others).
- Geographical level (Local, Regional, National, European, International).

2.2.1 Contexts of implementation

Partners have actively promoted the project to engage target groups, providing additional information and sharing project content. This more engaging communication phase aims to result in a significant impact on knowledge acquisition and active participation of the target groups involved.

In total, information events organized by the Consortium were:

Table 2. Comparison and total of information activities

	YEAR 1		YEAR 2		TOTAL	
	Nr. events	Participants	Nr. events	Participants	Nr. events	Participants
Conferences	10	2,927	23 + 5 ³	2,949	33	5,876
Information meetings	11	247	30	695	41	942
Events	6	1,340	5	3,157	11	4,497
Clustering Activities	1	24			1	24
Scientific cooperation			2	69	2	69
Collaboration with EU-funded projects			5	435	5	435
TOTAL	28	4,538	65	7,305	93	12,006

Table 2–

Detailed tables per partner can be found in Annex 4 (tables 11 and 12).

The general impact of the information activities has been good, with a total of 6708 persons reached. Partners have organized, and participated in various events to promote the project and its objectives, aiming to attract more participants to the Community of Schools and the Network of Stakeholders. The information meetings have garnered significant attendance and laid the groundwork for directly implementing of project activities.

An important aspect of the project communication has been also the participation in conferences thus involving the scientific educational community. A detailed description of the conferences in which the project has been presented can be found in Annex 5

³ No confirmed data on the number of participants for 5 conferences. The actual total number of conferences in which the partners have participated is 28.

2.2.2 Target groups

The Consortium has involved the widest possible audience in the events and activities in order to motivate them to become an active part of the LET'S CARE project and to make them aware of its values and aims.

The audience involved consists of the following target groups:

Table 3. Comparison and total of the target groups involved in the information activities

	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	TOTAL
Students	587	3,099	3,686
Families	83	36	119
Education scientific communities	205	548	753
Teachers	908	2,394	3,302
Schools	2,236	278	2,514
Policy Makers & Authorities	155	154	309
European Policy Makers	5	146	151
NGOs and advocacy organisations	27	109	136
General public	303	411	704
Others	2	100	102
TOTAL	4,511	7,275	11,786

A detailed table per partner can be found in Annex 4 (Table 13).

As the data clearly shows, the partners mainly focused on involving teachers (2324) in the events in order to invite them to the Community of Schools. To raise awareness on Safe Education even for the next generation of teachers and in general in the academical world, the partners involved in the event also include university students involved (future teachers) and representatives of the education scientific community.

During the information events an important number of policymakers and authorities at the local and European levels were involved. The general public has been involved during conferences and other events (in person and online).

2.2.3 Geographical level

As in the first year of the project, the partners implemented most of the events at the local level, reaching 3577 persons (over 2 times more than the previous report). The production of further results to be disseminated improved also the participation in international events and the consequent number of stakeholders involved.

Table 4. Comparison and total geographical impact of the information activities

	YEAR 1		YEAR 2		TOTAL	
	Nr. events	Participants	Nr. events	Participants	Nr. events	Participants
International	3	235	6	1,009	9	1,244
European	3	309	5	870	8	1,179
National	4	2,384	19	1,739	23	4,123
Local /Regional	18	1,610	34	3,657	52	5,267
TOTAL	28	4,538	64	7,275	92	11,813

Detailed tables can be found in Annex 4 (Tables 14 and 15).

3. Results of the dissemination activities

3.1 Knowledge

The “knowledge” level of dissemination refers to activities that allow the main target groups to increase their understanding of LET’S CARE specific topics. Partners have implemented specific training courses and workshops related to the main educational strategies and approaches that can support Safe Teaching and Safe School. These events emphasized LET’S CARE's core objective to create an inclusive and innovative educational environment that is responsive to students' emotional and relational needs. Safe Schools will enhance learning by fostering cognitive, emotional, and social development. The participation of the target groups demonstrates the stakeholders’ interest in the LET’S CARE approach.

Training topics include, among others:

- LET’S CARE Safe Education model.
- Practical strategies for inclusive teaching.
- Pedagogical methods that prioritize learner-centered education.
- Shifting from traditional grading to narrative assessment to support children’s development and well-being.
- Develop a school organization that puts the well-being of the students at the center of its action.
- Managing complex classes respecting the students.

The analysis of the implementation results follows three main aspects:

- Dissemination Contexts (Workshops and Training events).
- Target groups (Students, Students’ Families, Education Scientific Community, Teachers, Schools, Policy Makers & Authorities, European Policy Makers, NGOs & Advocacy Organizations, General Public, Others).
- Geographical level (Local, Regional, National, European, International).

3.1.1 *Dissemination Contexts*

The field research partners have organized training events to facilitate the teachers participating in the Community of Schools and the Network of Stakeholders to implement the Safe Teaching approach. These training courses have been a way to further involve teachers and make them more aware of the objectives and the holistic approach that LET’S CARE is promoting.

Analysing and comparing the data:

Table 5. Comparison and total of the knowledge activities

	YEAR 1		YEAR 2		TOTAL	
	Nr. events	Participants	Nr. events	Participants	Nr. events	Participants
Training events and workshops	42	4,302	118 (+6 ⁴)	19,346	160	23,648
TOTAL	42	4,302	118	19,346	160	23,648

Detailed tables with the number of training events and participants can be found in Annex 6 (tables 16 and 17).

3.1.2 Target groups

The figures show that the interest of teachers, families, and school directors has been consistent. A high number of teachers (7705) have improved their understanding of the Safe Teaching approach. POLO and KITE have given the opportunity to the teachers to follow the trainings asynchronously.

An important element in this second year of the project is the involvement of the families in starting the building of a Safe learning community and improving the cooperation with the school for the well-being of the students.

Table 6. Comparison and total of the target groups involved in the knowledge activities

	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	TOTAL
Students	140	277	417
Families		6,441	6,441
Education Scientific Community	5	38	43
Teachers	1,889	7,705	9,594
Schools	20	451	471
Policy Makers & Authorities		72	72

⁴No defined data on the numbers of participants for 6 training events. The actual total number of implemented training events is 124.

NGOs & Advocacy Organization		2	2
General Public	2,248	6	2,254
Asynchronous learners		4,354	4,345
TOTAL	4,302	19,346	23,648

A detailed table with target groups per partner can be found in Annex 6 (table 18).

All these events have created an important starting point for the future sustainability of the project and the participation of the schools in the research. From the social point of view, these events have raised awareness on the need to change the school approach by bringing the students' emotional safety at the centre of the educational action.

3.1.3 Geographical level

As for the information meetings, the partners have worked more at the local and regional level, organizing training courses for teachers and events for families. Action at the local level is crucial to ensure the long-term engagement of the schools.

Table 7. Comparison and total of the geographical impact of the knowledge activities

	YEAR 1		YEAR 2		TOTAL	
	Nr. events	Participants	Nr. events	Participants	Nr. events	Participants
International	5	157			5	157
European			3	427	3	427
National	31	3,828	19	17,715	50	21,543
Local /Regional	6	317	33	1204	39	1521
TOTAL	42	4302	118	19,346	97	23,648

Detailed tables with the number of events and participants can be found in Annex 5 (tables 19 and 20).

4. Results of Exploitation

During the first year, the focus was on implementing the IPR. This initial phase concentrated on identifying and categorizing the background IP contributed by each partner to the Consortium, ensuring a clear understanding of the pre-existing assets and the rights each member holds over them. This identification process was essential for establishing a baseline and preventing future conflicts regarding the IP ownership generated during the project. The foundation for managing the foreground IP generated throughout the project was also laid, following the terms set out in the Grant and Consortium Agreements.

In the second year, from September 2023 (M12) to September 2024 (M24), efforts have been directed towards identifying of key results and evaluating key ideas, with the continued collaboration of the Consortium. The following sections will provide a comprehensive and detailed account of both processes undertaken during the second year of the exploitation phase of the LET'S CARE project.

4.1 Identification of Key Results

The identification of key results is a crucial component of the LET'S CARE project's exploitation phase. This section provides an overview of the systematic process undertaken during the second year to identify, gather, and evaluate results with potential for exploitation. The procedure consisted of two main steps: first, collecting comprehensive information on identified key results from all project partners, and second, conducting a thorough analysis of these results to assess their potential for commercialization and broader application.

The following subsections will outline each step in detail, beginning with gathering information on key results and concluding with analysing their exploitation potential. This comprehensive evaluation involved close collaboration with the Consortium, ensuring that all contributions were carefully documented and assessed. Given the confidential nature of some information collected, not all data can be disclosed within this deliverable. However, this section aims to provide a clear and structured summary of the key findings, as well as the changes and developments observed throughout this phase.

The findings presented here will serve as a foundation for the continued exploitation efforts, which will ultimately be compiled in the final report at the end of the project.

4.1.1 *Gathering information on identified key results*

In May 2024 (M20), all project partners were initially consulted to ascertain any changes that may have arisen during the development.

Subsequently, in July (M22), following the collection of responses, ZIC supplied the partners with an Excel template specifically designed to gather comprehensive information on each identified outcome. This template comprises multiple sheets, each dedicated to the various results deemed suitable for potential exploitation.

In succession, find detail a table of the questionnaires that provides information on each Key Exploitation Results (KERs) associated with each partner.

Table 8. Key Exploitation Results (KERs) associated with each partner

RKA.1.1 Let's care platforms		
Exploitable result 1.1.1	LET'S CARE hub	COM
Exploitable result 1.1.2	Safe teaching lab	
RKA. 1.2 Let's care Research Resource		
Exploitable result 1.2.1	Safe Education Model publications	Partners' autho LET'S CARE Consortium
Exploitable result 1.2.2	Safe Education database	
Exploitable result 1.2.3	Safe Teaching Practices wiki-database	
Exploitable result 1.2.4	LET'S CARE Set of Variables	
RKA. 1.3 Let's care Tools		
Exploitable result 1.3.1	Safe Education indexes	COM, CID, FHV, POLO, PROMA, JEX ARID, PRSC, UCP, AIK, IPA, KITE
Exploitable result 1.3.2	Safe Learning e-profile	
Exploitable result 1.3.3	Safe Teaching assessment tools	
Exploitable result 1.3.4	Safe School Label	
RKA. 1.4 Let's care Trainings		
Exploitable result 1.4.1	Safe Teaching Training program	COM, CID, FHV, POLO, PROMA, JEX ARID, PRSC, UCP, AIK, IPA, KITE
Exploitable result 1.4.2	PAR Qualitative techniques.	
Exploitable result 1.4.3	Training on LET'S CARE tools.	
Exploitable result 1.4.4	Refined tools for peer observation.	
Exploitable result 1.4.5	Legal know-how on project implementation	
Exploitable result 1.4.6	Development of criteria for peer observation	
RKA. 1.5 Let's care know- How		
Exploitable result 1.5.1	Legal know-how on project implementation	TLX PROMA
Exploitable result 1.5.2	Development of criteria for peer observation	
RKA. 1.6 Let's care Policy Recommendations		
Exploitable result 1.6.1	Green paper / White paper	LET'S CARE Consortium
Exploitable result 1.6.2	Economic assessment	
Exploitable result 1.6.3	Safe School Label	

The questionnaires cannot be included in this deliverable due to their confidential nature. The information gathered through the questionnaire contains sensitive data that must remain confidential to protect competitive advantages and comply with privacy regulations.

The findings of this questionnaire will be used for an assessment of the potential of the business idea, whose results will be published in D6.6 at the end of the project.

Subsequently, the next phase involved conducting a thorough analysis of these results.

4.1.2 Analysis of key results potential for exploitation

As commented in Step 1. Gathering Information on Identified Key Results, ZIC asked for any changes that may have arisen during the course of development. The following table reports in detail the changes.

Table 9. Exploitation Results (KERs) associated with each partner, new changes

			New Changes
RKA.1.1 LET'S CARE platforms			
Exploitable result 1.1.1	LET'S CARE hub	COM	No changes
Exploitable result 1.1.2	Safe teaching lab		
Exploitable result 1.2.1	Safe Education Model publications	Partners' autho LET'S CARE Con- sortium	No changes
Exploitable result 1.2.2	Safe Education database		
Exploitable result 1.2.3	Safe Teaching Practices wiki- database		
Exploitable result 1.2.4	Let's Care Set of Variables		
RKA. 1.3 LET'S CARE Tools			
Exploitable result 1.3.1	Safe Education indexes	COM, CID, FHV, POLO, PROMA, JEX ARID, PRSC, UCP, AIK, IPA, KITE	New Change
Exploitable result 1.3.2	Safe Learning e-profile		
Exploitable result 1.3.3	Safe Teaching assessment tools		
Exploitable result 1.3.4	Safe School Label		
RKA. 1.4 LET'S CARE Trainings			
Exploitable result 1.4.1	Safe Teaching Training program	COM, CID, FHV, POLO, PROMA, JEX ARID, PRSC, UCP, AIK, IPA, KITE	No changes
Exploitable result 1.4.2	PAR Qualitative techniques.		
Exploitable result 1.4.3	Training on LET'S CARE tools.		
Exploitable result 1.4.4	Refined tools for peer observation.		
Exploitable result 1.4.5	Legal know-how on project imple- mentation		
Exploitable result 1.4.6	Development of criteria for peer observation		
RKA. 1.5 LET'S CARE know- How			
Exploitable result 1.5.1	Legal know-how on project imple-	TLX	No changes

	mentation	PROMA	
Exploitable result 1.5.2	Development of criteria for peer observation		
RKA. 1.6 LET'S CARE Policy Recommendations			
Exploitable result 1.6,1	Green paper / White paper	LET'S CARE Consortium	No changes
Exploitable result 1.6,2	Economic assessment		
Exploitable result 1.6,3	Safe School Label		

New Changes

Exploitable result 1.4.4 Refined tools for peer observation

JEX have worked directly with school centres instead of through educational programmes.

Initially, the plan has been to engage with schools by implementing educational programs or initiatives at a more general or institutional level. However, the change means that the project decided to engage directly with individual schools or school centers, allowing for more hands-on, tailored, and potentially immediate interaction.

This adjustment implies a more direct and personalized engagement with schools, where activities, training, or interventions are carried out in collaboration with the schools themselves rather than implementing a broader program that schools adapt to. This approach allows for more specific feedback, adaptation to the unique needs of each school, and a closer relationship between the project team and the educators involved.

The following outlines the consequences of the change:

- **Enhanced Customisation:** By working directly with school centres, the project can adapt its methods and tools to suit of each school’s specific needs and contexts, making the interventions more relevant and effective.
- **Increased Impact:** Direct engagement often results in a more profound impact, as the project team can address challenges and opportunities more effectively in real-time.
- **More Immediate Feedback:** This approach allows for quicker and more actionable feedback from teachers and staff, which can be used to refine the project's strategies and tools.
- **Potential Resource Intensiveness:** Direct engagement with schools may require more time and resources than implementing a broader program, potentially limiting the number of schools that can be reached.

Overall, this change indicates a shift towards a more tailored and hands-on approach, aiming for deeper integration and impact within individual school settings.

4.2 Evaluation of Key Ideas

Upon receiving the changes, including the forms, ZIC conducted a comprehensive analysis of the relevant information. LET'S CARE is a project aimed at developing an educational methodology, that employs various techniques. It is noteworthy to highlight the implementation of the PAR and Photovoice methodologies, both of which could potentially provide significant value to society in the future.

Furthermore, FHV has made significant progress in developing the LET'S CARE Hub platform subsystem, particularly with integrating the Le Sphinx tool for data collection. This tool is used to collect quantitative data, implement surveys, and analyze the resulting data. The implementation of questionnaires in English has been completed, and we are currently advancing with translations into other languages. Additionally, the design of certain sections of the LET'S CARE Hub has been enhanced to improve the overall user experience. Lastly, regarding the upcoming evaluation, the proposal includes the aggregation of the KERs for simplification purposes, and efforts will continue in this area to ensure the effective exploitation and dissemination of the project results.

Currently, the project is at an immature phase, and in the upcoming stages, new changes and results, which have yet to be defined, will be more observable. In this regard, Let's Care continues to evolve, with results to be published in D6.6 at the end of the project. Lastly, concerning the upcoming evaluation, the proposal includes the aggregation of the KERS for simplification purposes, and efforts will continue in this area.

4.3 Future Activities

The upcoming steps in the following months will focus on the exploitation strategy, the update of the IP management plan, and establishing networks with other projects and initiatives. These activities will ensure that the results and knowledge generated by the LET'S CARE project are effectively managed, protected, and leveraged to maximize their impact and long-term sustainability. The planned actions for each stage of this process are outlined below. It can be outlined in the subsequent three stages: Exploitation Strategy Generation, Updated IP Management Plan and Networking with Projects & Initiatives.

- **Exploitation Strategy Generation**, LET'S CARE will develop an integrated exploitation strategy that combines joint and individual plans to foster collaboration among partners. Each organization's plan will contribute to a unified strategy, ensuring synergy and maximizing impact. Using methods such as Lean Canvas and Exploitation Workshops, led by ZIC, partners will create tailored strategies for high-potential results, which will be documented in Deliverable D6.5.

- **Updated IP Management Plan**, with clearly defined business models, an IP management strategy will be implemented to protect the knowledge generated by the project. This will involve mapping existing patents and providing recommendations for protection. An updated IP Management Plan will be presented in Deliverable D6.6 by Month 48.
- **Networking with Projects & Initiatives**, efforts will focus on building connections with other projects and initiatives, including aligning exploitation strategies, participating in joint events, and engaging with potential business stakeholders. Discussions will also cover the ongoing maintenance and development of scientific outputs beyond the project's conclusion, which will be presented in Deliverable D6.6 by Month 48.

5. Conclusions

The analysis of the impact of the dissemination and communication activities during the project's second year shows a great improvement in the results of persons informed about and involved in the project's activities. The partners have reached the main target groups: teachers, school directors, the scientific community, public administrations, and policymakers, according to their possibilities. The high commitment of the fieldwork partners has resulted in great participation and interest of the stakeholders, paving the way for large-scale data collection during the third year.

The **communication** activities remarkably impacted the general public, showing the partners' commitment to sharing the project's contents and activities. In total, 7,305 participants have been involved in information activities, in detail 2,949 in conferences, 695 in information meetings and 3661 in other events.

Through information meetings, presentations in conferences, clustering events and training courses related to the project, the Consortium has addressed all the project's target groups, reaching:

- 3,123 students.
- 36 students' families.
- 548 representatives of the education scientific community.
- 278 schools.
- 2,394 teachers and educators.
- 154 policymakers.
- 146 European policymakers.
- 115 representatives of NGOs and advocacy organisations.

The **dissemination** activities have met the interest and the participation of a considerable number of target groups involved in the project activities: 19,346 persons have attended the LET'S CARE-related training activities and workshops implemented by the consortium members, in particular 7,705 teachers.

The analysis of **exploitation**, LET'S CARE is a project aimed at developing an educational methodology, employing various techniques. It is noteworthy to highlight that the PAR and Photovoice methodologies, as well as the development of the Let's Care Hub platform subsystem, particularly with the integration of the Le Sphinx tool for data collection, have all been identified as having significant potential for social impact. Currently, the project is at an immature phase, and in the upcoming stages, new changes and results, which have yet to be defined, will be more observable. In this regard, LET'S CARE continues to evolve, with results to be published in D6.6 at the end of the project.

Annex 1 – Communication Material

4 STAKEHOLDERS NETWORK PRESENTATION LEAFLETS

Available in English and translated at: <https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/f/5633994>

Sample in English:

WOULD YOU LIKE TO CONTRIBUTE TO A **SAFE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT** FOR ALL LEARNERS?

Together We Can!

In the framework of the Horizon Europe project **LET'S CARE**, a **Stakeholders Network** has been established to gather professionals and organisation in the educational sector, with the aim of fostering a **Safe Education** in order to prevent **exclusion, underachievement, disengagement** and **school dropout**.

JOIN NOW
the **LET'S CARE**
STAKEHOLDERS NETWORK
letscaresproject.eu

Let's care
BUILDING SAFE AND Caring SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL WELLBEING
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT
Priority
of the European Union

For more information
CLICK HERE

To subscribe
SCAN HERE!
letscaresproject.eu

Figure 3. - Invitation to join the Network of Stakeholders

Sample in English:

Figure 4. - Leaflet about the Network of Stakeholders

5 STAKEHOLDERS NETWORK PRESENTATION IMAGE FOR SOCIAL MEDIA

Available in English and translated at: <https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/f/5633994>

Sample in English:

Figure 5. Image for the social networks of the Network of Stakeholders

6 NEWSLETTERS

Available in English and translated at: <https://letscaresproject.eu/newsletter/>

Samples of the first pages:

Figure 6. First page of the 2nd Newsletter

Figure 7. First page of the 3rd Newsletter

Figure 8. First page of the 4th Newsletter

7 COMMUNICATION MATERIAL FOR THE FIRST LET'S CARE TRANSNATIONAL CONFERENCE

Sample in English:

Figure 9. Promotion picture for the first LET'S CARE conference

8 SECOND PROMOTIONAL VIDEO

Available at: <https://tubedu.org/w/1uvWQgUTJgX2JzzFMwGWan>

Sample screenshot:

Figure 10. Screenshot of the 2nd Promotional video

Annex 2 – List of the web links with Let's care references

Web pages and media articles

<https://www.europole.org/lets-care-2/>

<https://www.europole.org/agenda-corso-freinet-2023/>

<https://www.europole.org/gli-insegnanti-e-il-futuro-delle-nostre-democrazie-giornata-di-studio-con-philippe-meirieu-a-verona/>

<https://www.europole.org/scuole-senza-voti/>

<https://www.europole.org/una-scuola-senza-voto/>

<https://www.europole.org/la-valutazione-degli-alunni-nella-prospettiva-di-una-scuola-innovativa-ed-efficace/>

<https://www.europole.org/una-scuola-che-educa-alla-nonviolenza-con-la-nonviolenza/>

<https://www.europole.org/workshop-sul-photovoice/>

<https://www.europole.org/comportamenti-sfidanti-ed-oppositivi-in-classe-tra-bisogni-educativi-speciali-e-gestione-delle-classi-difficili/>

<https://www.europole.org/segno-disegno-e-scrittura-da-0-a-6-anni-come-e-perche-rispettare-i-tempi-dei-bambini/>

<https://www.europole.org/laffettivita-e-la-sessualita-in-bambine-i-e-ragazze-i-con-le-caratteristiche-dellautismo/>

<https://www.europole.org/la-scuola-inclusiva-e-quella-che-vuole-e-sa-accogliere/>

<https://www.europole.org/montessorie-robotica/>

<https://www.europole.org/webinar-su-le-indicazioni-nazionali-per-una-scuola-come-bene-comune/>

<https://www.europole.org/due-giornate-formative-voglia-di-comunita-educante/>

<https://agenparl.eu/2024/04/09/26-27-aprile-verona-vandana-shiva-special-guest-alla-conferenza-internazionale-del-polo-europeo-della-conoscenza-la-scuola-come-cardine-del-futuro-della-nostra-civilta/>

<https://www.pressenza.com/it/2024/04/prossimo-futuro-n-169-22-28-aprile/>

<https://www.tecnicaldella scuola.it/una-scuola-a-misura-di-bambino-importante-convegno-internazionale-a-verona>

<https://soloscuola.it/2024/04/22/una-scuola-a-misura-di-bambino-importante-convegno-internazionale-a-verona/>

<https://www.indire.it/2024/04/23/scuola-e-futuro-a-verona-due-conferenze-internazionali-del-polo-europeo-della-conoscenza/>

<https://www.informazione.it/c/41C644E0-D631-4D7D-BD31-8F1EDB9F56FC/Una-scuola-a-misura-di-bambino-importante-convegno-internazionale-a-Verona-aperto-a-tutti>

https://www.redattoresociale.it/article/una_scuola_a_misura_dei_bambini

<https://www.rainews.it/tgr/veneto/notiziari/video/2024/04/TGR-Veneto-del-26042024-ore-1930-0eb58f11-3db4-4fa4-9fda-9b785eaa1a36.html>

<https://www.telearena.it/programmi-di-informazione/tg/tg-sera-1.10690916>

<https://www.telepace.it/puntate/telepace-news-26-aprile-2024/>

<https://telenuovo.it/attualita/2024/04/26/ecco-una-scuola-a-misura-dei-bambini-video>

<https://www.peacelink.it/calendario/event.php?id=11459>

https://www.redattoresociale.it/article/una_scuola_di_immigrazione_culturale_ed_emigrazione_sociale

<https://www.telepace.it/puntate/telepace-news-29-aprile-2024/>

<https://ignatianum.edu.pl/artukul/let-s-care-budowanie-bezpiecznych-i-troskliwych-szkol-w-celu-wspierania-wlaczania-edukacyjnego-i-osiagniec-szkolnych>

<https://ignatianum.edu.pl/artukul/let-s-care-hub>

<https://www.fhv.at/en/research/business-informatics/projects/ongoing-projects/lets%20care>

<https://www.fhv.at/forschung/forschungsnews/2024/lets-care>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-10-01

<https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-11-01>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-12-01

<https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2024-01-01>

<https://www.panrs.lt/svietimo-centras-igyvendina-ambicinga-projekta-lets-care/>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2024-02-01

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2024-03-01

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2024-04-01

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2024-05-01

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2024-06-01

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2024-07-01

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2024-09-01

<https://prsc.lt/lt/erasmus-projektas-peec>

<https://www.timelex.eu/en/blog/minors-vulnerable-participants-social-research-activities>

Social Media

https://www.facebook.com/groups/514090329523918/posts/1428468471419428/?locale=bg_BG

https://www.facebook.com/nu.raidavica?locale=bg_BG

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/514090329523918/posts/1484828645783410>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/514090329523918/posts/1488308568768751/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/514090329523918/posts/1489453268654281/>

<https://www.facebook.com/100009331232889/videos/1148734019771821>

<https://www.facebook.com/1803785281/videos/1825630557931918/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/514090329523918/posts/1502975940635347>

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid02bDbF6hUL3vu6TVbiN9adnzV8JRG86qu3XojHp5iJxVFxp8JKHLv2ZBNC4HuUexUPI&id=100053436887288

https://www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid0FABDYuBPZUX5bKyZ4Q5RDB67WYNvHWvy7yu7SBuV8HWxUNT651G8cqpyusBfbd7l&id=100038978642950

<https://www.facebook.com/nu.raidavica/posts/pfbid0evuRZ4sGzqY9RFWf6TdpKoL7QC5EtaixXTYBsut58JSnaFb86ZrmfYe4paiQEufWl>

<https://www.facebook.com/prsc.lt/posts/pfbid0pXEDPh13E1Qhak2G5ysj9btmMF4nXgxVXvjMHfaJP3V41y6C2ybFd69oNJujUsDTl>

Annex 3 – Results of the communication activities - Awareness

ONLINE COMMUNICATION

Table 10 Online Communication (views)

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Media articles	*				*			151,729		13,800	7			165,536
Social media	*						719	339		100				1,158
Mailing lists	*					25		65,834	856	60				66,775
Promotional videos								232						232
TOTAL	0	0	0	0	0	25	719	217,902	856	13,960	7	0	0	233,469

* = No data available on website views

Figure 11. – Online communication (views)

Annex 4 – Results of the communication activities – Information

NUMBER OF INFORMATION EVENTS

Table 11 Number of information events per partner

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Conferences	3	2		7			2	3	1	2		3		23
Information meetings	2	11					10	1	2	2		2		30
Events	1					1	2		1					5
Scientific Cooperation	2													2
Collaboration with EU-funded projects		3						1		1				5
TOTAL	8	16	0	7	0	1	14	4	4	5	0	5	0	65

Number of information events

Figure 12. – Number of information events

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER INFORMATION EVENT

Table 12 Number of participants/audiences per information event and partner

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Conferences	246	120		1294			335	518	12	131		293		2,949
Information meetings	18	315					218	50	49	21		24		695
Events	2,000					130	823		204					3,157
Scientific Cooperation	69													69
Collaboration with EU-funded projects		380						30		25				435
TOTAL	2,333	815	0	1,294	0	130	1,376	598	265	177	0	317	0	7,305

Number of participants per information event

Figure 13. – Number of participants per information event

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER TARGET GROUP REACHED IN INFORMATION EVENTS

Table 13 Number of participants/audiences per target group and partner

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Students	2,065	215				100	716	27						3,123
Families							36							36
Education Scientific Community	137	320		12		10	5	10	6	5		43		548
Teachers	54	170		776		20	464	261	259	130		260		2,394
Schools				246			22			3		7		278
Policy Makers & Authorities	19	10		13			55	16		34		7		154
European	2			143				1						146

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROM A	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Policy Makers														
NGOs & Advocacy Organizations	55			8			14	33		5				115
General Public				96			65	250						411
Others		100												100
TOTAL	2,332	815	0	1,294	0	130	1,377	568	265	177	0	317	0	7305

Number of participants per target group

Figure 14. – Number of participants/audiences per target group

NUMBER OF INFORMATION EVENTS PER GEOGRAPHICAL IMPACT

Table 14 Number of information events per geographical impact

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PRO MA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
International	1			1			1			1		2		6
European		2		2		1		1						6
National	4			3			3	4	2	2		1		19
Regional / Local	3	14		1			10		2	2		2		34
TOTAL	8	16	0	7	0	1	14	4	4	5	0	5	0	65

Number of information events per Geographical impact

Figure 15. Number of information events per geographical impact

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER GEOGRAPHICAL IMPACT AND PER PARTNER

Table 15 Number of participants / audiences per geographical impact and per partner

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PRO MA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
International	112			143			118			25		43		441
European		300		440		130		30						900
National	203			699			302	568	216	69		250		2,307
Regional / Local	2,018	515		12			956		49	83		24		3,657
TOTAL	2,333	815	0	1,294	0	130	1,376	598	265	177	0	317	0	7,275

Number of participants per geographical impact

Figure 16. Number of participants / audiences per geographical impact

Annex 5 – Participation in conferences

TEACHERS AND THE FUTURE OF OUR DEMOCRACIES.

SEMINAR WITH PHILIPPE MEIRIEU

Partner: POLO

Place: Verona (Italy)

Date: 18/10/2023

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

Full-day reflection seminar on the social and political importance of teaching action, with the keynote speech of Philippe Meirieu, Emeritus Professor of Educational Sciences at the University Lumière Lyon II; he has led a lot of research on schools and participated in the elaboration of important school reforms in France. POLO has organised this seminar with the sponsorship of the Municipality of Verona. The event aimed to have an important socio-political resonance, thanks to the mayor's intervention and the active participation of the Councillor for Education and School Policies and other educational policy makers of the province of Verona. The initial part of the day was dedicated to a plenary discussion, while during the afternoon, the teachers worked in discussion groups led by experts.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://www.europole.org/gli-insegnanti-e-il-futuro-delle-nostre-democrazie-giornata-di-studio-con-philippe-meirieu-a-verona/>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

The LET'S CARE 4 pillars holistic approach has been presented as a guiding framework for the day, especially the Safe Community.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Important hints for the policy recommendations have been collected.

The municipality of Verona has been involved in the activity and has supported the implementation of the project.

EVIDENCE

<https://tubedu.org/w/4oXKEyrfwiTJZ17LcVoBz2>

A CHILD-FRIENDLY SCHOOL

Partner: POLO

Place: Verona (Italy)

Date: 26/04/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

In cooperation with the Erasmus+ KA3 Social Innovation project Schools Plastic Free Movement, POLO has organized a conference presenting the main teaching strategies that could support the Safe Teaching, the Safe School and the well-being of children.

The conference has been organized with the sponsorship of the Municipality of Verona, and policy makers from different fields have participated. Experts, researchers, and representatives of civil society organizations and associations presented different practices and approaches.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://www.europole.org/conferenza2024/>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

The LET'S CARE Safe Education approach has been presented as a guiding framework for the day.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

The municipality of Verona has been involved in the activity and has supported the implementation of the project. New schools and organizations joined the Network of Stakeholders.

EVIDENCE

<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/f/5632306>

COMMUNITY-BASED PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH (CBPR) IN CLINICAL SETTINGS

Partner: COMILLAS

Place: Madrid (Spain)

Date: 27/06/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

On the 27th of June, the 1st UNINPSI Research Conference was held with the participation of professors from the Department of Psychology of the Pontifical University of Comillas, researchers from chairs and institutes of the University, UNINPSI therapists, doctoral candidates, undergraduate and master students from the Faculty of Social Sciences and researchers from other institutions.

The programme consisted of three conferences, one of which was given by one of the researchers of the LET'S CARE project, Dr. Ángela Ordóñez-Carabaño, who spoke about Community-Based Participatory Research (CBPR) in clinical contexts.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://eventos.comillas.edu/117155/detail/i-jornada-de-investigacion-uninpsi.html?private=6e215352ecae0aef691a>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

The co-creation research approach, including the Community-Based Participatory Research (CBPR) Approach.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

The conference was well received by the audience, most of whom were unfamiliar with participatory research methods. It gave rise to a wide range of questions on the subject, and subsequent meetings focused on the inclusion of this methodology in other research projects.

EVIDENCE

<https://eventos.comillas.edu/117155/programme/i-jornada-de-investigacion-uninpsi.html?private=6e215352ecae0aef691a>

<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/oWKgsg2fsabQJdk>

XXVIII INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY FOR SOCIAL PEDIATRICS AND CHILD HEALTH CONGRESS

Partner: **COMILLAS**

Place: **Valencia (Spain)**

Date: **17/11/2023**

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

Keynote presentation on Multisystemic advocacy for the development of resilient in ROUND TABLE 1: Attachment and resilience: creating bonds in the XXVIII International Society for Social Pediatrics and Child health Congress in Valencia 16/18 November 2023.

[XXVI Congreso SEPS / XXXVIII Congreso ISSOP - Viernes 17 \(youtube.com\)](#)

EVIDENCE

<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/f/3362364>

[2023 SEPSValencia AB.pdf](#)

CONGRESS OF CATHOLIC SCHOOLS: INSPIRING MEETINGS

Partner: **COMILLAS**

Place: **Granada (Spain)**

Date: **26/11/2023**

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

Colloquium "Listening and caring" at the "Congress of Catholic Schools: inspiring meetings" held in Granada on November 24-26, 2023, and organised by the Federation of Catholic Schools of Spain to highlight the dimension of care in the education system and where the LET'S CARE project aims were presented.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://inspiradoresdeencuentros.esuelascatolicas.es/>

JESUITES EDUCACIÓ HEADS CONFERENCE

Partner: **COMILLAS**

Place: **Barcelona (Spain)**

Date: **01/03/2024**

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

Keynote speech "Finding the roots of hope: buildings schools than care" during Jesuites Educació Heads Conference, organized by the Jesuites Educació Foundation (<https://www.fje.edu>), that took place in Barcelona, Spain, 1st March 2024 with the aim of highlighting the dimension of care in the education system in relation with children and adolescents mental health, school well-being and outcomes and where the lets care project aims were presented.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

[La Fundació Jesuïtes Educació | Fundació Jesuïtes Educació \(fje.edu\)](#)

ESCUELAS QUE CUIDAN Y ENSEÑAN A CUIDAR

Partner: COMILLAS

Place: Los Negrales (Spain)

Date: 19/01/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

Conference entitled "Escuelas que cuidan y enseñan a cuidar" in the meeting of management teams and the entity in charge of the network of educational centres of the Teresian Association in Spain that took place in Los Negrales (Spain) from 19th to 21st January 2024.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

[FDO Certificado formación EEDD.pdf](#)

JECSE PRIMARY SCHOOL HEADS CONFERENCE

Partner: COMILLAS

Place: Soutelo (Portugal)

Date: 23/01/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

During JECSE Primary School Heads Conference, organized by the Jesuit European Committee for Primary and Secondary Education (JECSE), that took place in Soutelo, Portugal, from 23rd to 26th January 2024.

With the aim of highlighting the dimension of care in the education system in relation to children and adolescents' mental health, school well-being and outcomes and where the Let's Care project aims were presented to participants from Northern Belgium, Southern Belgium, France, Spain, Ireland, the United Kingdom, Portugal, Italy, Malta, the Netherlands, Hungary, and Poland.

APRENDER SEGUROS: ESCUELAS QUE CUIDAN (ASEC) - SAFE LEARNING: CARING SCHOOLS

Partner: COMILLAS

Place: Madrid (Spain)

Date: 1/07/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

Second session (3h) of Module 1 (Promoting safety in the classroom) of the training program "Aprender Seguros: Escuelas que Cuidan (ASEC) -Safe Learning: Caring schools-". ASEC objectives are to sensitize and train teachers to detect, understand and manage the affective needs of children at school, to assist in the establishment of good care partnerships with families, and to integrate a model of care and intervention focused on the security of relationships into the coordination/management teams. This is a 19 hour-training, and it is made up of 3 modules (9, 6 and 4 hours, respectively).

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/f/5632449>

SOCIAL PEDAGOGY IN THE SERVICE OF MAN AND THE COMMUNITY

Partner: AIK

Place: Krakow (Poland)

Date: 16/04/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The field of social pedagogy is expanding due to its development, reinterpretation of previous achievements, and ongoing threats to individuals, communities, and humanity. Social pedagogues cannot be passive in the face of these growing threats and must engage in scientific discussion and share observations to build community and do the common good.

The conference participants reflected on key issues of contemporary social pedagogy and social work, including education for coexistence, social change, threats, social work as an area of activity, and protective factors of the school environment. The conference gathered a large group of researchers, which facilitated the dissemination of information about the project.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://wse.amu.edu.pl/kalendarz-wydarzen-wse/zycie-wydzialu/konferencje/konferencja-naukowa-z-okazji-jubileuszu-55-lecia-poznanskiej-pedagogiki-spoecznej>

<https://uniwersyteckie.pl/wydarzenia/pedagogika-spoeczna-uam-ma-55-lat>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

The speech focused on the protective factors of the school environment and strengthening resilience in the family. Resilience is the ability to adapt positively to significant adversities. Shaping resilience is a crucial educational task for schools and families due to socio-cultural changes. Protective factors, including immune and adaptive resources, specific values, and the environmental potential of school culture, play a significant role in shaping and strengthening resilience. The paper aimed to scientifically reflect on these factors and their impact on individual and family resilience to promote personal development and improve quality of life.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Presenting a paper at the conference made it possible to spread information about the project, develop new contacts and receive feedback from researchers in the field of education.

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE "COLORS AND SHADES OF EVERYDAY LIFE"

Partner: AIK

Place: Krakow (Poland)

Date: 22-23/05/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The study of everyday life in the social sciences focuses on the individual and their interpersonal relationships, which are the foundation of humanity. The study of everyday life has placed anthropological, social, and cultural issues related to the spaces of modern man's everyday life at the center of interest. We have made issues related to emotions, experiences, social identities, cultural changes, or the mental well-being of modern man the subject of discussion. We want to look at micro and macro worlds, individual contexts of everyday life, and show the spectrum of today's existence, full of complex and extremely dynamic social, cultural, technological, and economic processes.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://ignatianum.edu.pl/miedzynarodowa-konferencja-naukowa-barwy-i-odcienie-zycia-osobiste-edukacyjne-spoeczne-i-kulturowe-przestrzenie-codziennosci>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

During the poster session, the assumptions of the LET'S CARE project and the activities carried out to popularise the project were presented.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Presenting at the Conference gave the opportunity to connect with the scientific community, with theoreticians and practitioners and to receive feedback from professionals in related fields. The poster session increased the reach of information about the idea and activities of the LET'S CARE project. The message reached not only the conference participants, but also AIK students, who had the opportunity to get to know more about the key issues for the project.

POST-COVID RELATIONS IN SCHOOL

Partner: **ARID**

Place: **Limanowa (Poland)**

Date: **25/01/2024**

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The conference was devoted post-covid broken relationship in school environment and ways of recovering them. This conference was organized in the high school in Limanowa, Małopolska voivodship. As a part of the conference ARID Association has presented LET'S CARE project in front of teachers from local schools but also in front of local policy makers from Limanowa and other communities (majors of local communities).

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

During the conference ARID Association has presented the general aims of the project and presented the first results like the analyses of the research of the interviews with teachers and families. ARID has also invited local schools to the participation in the project's CoS.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

As a result, ARID has got promise that they will join the CoS and will help us in the further steps of the project. Also one of the major counties (Tymbar) was very interested and promised to disseminate information about the project to the local schools.

ICE IEEE/ITMC

Partner: **FHV**

Place: **Madeira (Portugal)**

Date: **24-28/06/2024**

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The ICE/IEEE conference, hosted during MDT Week in Madeira (PT), is an international event that focused on “Digital Transformation on Engineering, Technology and Innovation”. The conference attracts a diverse audience of stakeholders, including researchers, academics and industry professionals.

The geographical impact of the event is substantial, with participants coming from various parts of the world. The paper was presented at this conference because its goals align with the event’s focus on digital transformation and innovation. Moreover, because the conference was international, it provided the project with the opportunity to enhance its visibility on a global scale.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://mdtweek.digit-madeira.pt/ice/>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

The scholarly paper presented, entitled “Agile Requirements Engineering as a Service: the Co-Creation of the LET’S CARE Hub” addresses the challenges in engineering Information and Knowledge-Management Systems within dynamic environments and diverse stakeholder requirements. By conducting a systematic literature review, the paper presents a framework for agile requirements engineering that enhances dynamic co-creation of digital artefacts, such as our LET’S CARE Hub.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Presenting at ICE/IEEE gave the opportunity to connect with the scientific community, receive feedback from professionals in related fields, and increase its visibility.

A HOLISTIC APPROACH IN PRE-SCHOOL AND PRIMARY EDUCATION

Partner: KITE

Place: Varna (Bulgaria)

Date: 4-5/06/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The event was attended by more than 500 teachers and principals from educational institutions across the country, representatives of institutions, non-governmental organisations, educational experts and others. Deputy Mayor Pavel Popov has shared the experience and plans of the

Municipality of Varna in the panel on "Regional Innovations for Better Preschool and Primary School Education" The main focus of the conference was the importance of the supportive environment, play, technology and innovative approaches in education. Successful practices in the field of social and emotional education, practical STEAM training, project-based learning, Montessori Method and creative technologies for holistic education have been shared. Issues such as school readiness, adaptation and continuity between pre-school and primary school education will also be discussed.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://cct.bg/national-conference-preschool-education/>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

Innovative approaches to inclusive education.

Children's well-being and success at the heart of education.

Sharing good practices – Social and emotional education.

From kindergarten to school – school readiness, adaptation and continuity between preschool and early school education.

The playful approach in the professional development of teachers.

Policies, strategies and good practices of municipal administrations in the field of preschool education.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Networking contacts: new stakeholders involved

ANY OTHER IMPORTANT INFORMATION TO BE ADDED

The Mayor of Varna Blagomir Kotsev welcomed the participants in the conference and emphasized the commitment of the municipality to quality education. "The urban environment is essential for their formation from an early age. As mayor, I am aware of the enormous responsibility I bear for creating conditions in which our children develop as full-fledged individuals and responsible citizens of our society," Kotsev said.

EVIDENCE

<https://classroomtech.bg/conference2024-opening/> Ministry of education prof. Galin Tzokov opens the conference

<https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=864783025683902&set=gm.926566712486312&id&orvanity=907039451105705> (Picture and Agenda)

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY IN THE MODERN DIGITAL AND MULTICULTURAL SPACE

Partner: KITE

Place: Yelets (Russian Federation)

Date: 18-19/04/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The work of the conference took place in 8 sectional sessions, in which more than 100 researchers participated. Lecturers, PhD students and students from the South-West University (Bulgaria) took part with 18 reports. The plenary report of Assist. ace. Dr. Miroslav Terziyski, dedicated to innovative STEM technologies in Bulgarian education. Plenary reports were also presented by the Head of the Department of Design, Art Education and Technology at the I. A. Bunin State University Prof. Dr. Victoria Maltseva, art critic Matteo Michello from Milan (Italy), Igor Orlov from Lipetsk State Technical University and others.

XV International Scientific and Practical Conference "Development of Creativity in the Modern Digital and Multicultural Space". The articles deal with the historical, theoretical, practical, spiritual and moral aspects of the formation and development of the creativity of the personality, as well as the complex spatio-temporal processes of the interaction of philosophies, high and mass arts, worldview created by different peoples. The publication is addressed to researchers, graduate students, students, practitioners in the field of education, to those interested in priority areas of development.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://fped.swu.bg/bg/newsbg/78-2024-04-22-14-20-44>

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Interest of the scientific community

A SCHOOL FOR EVERYONE. INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: THEORETICAL APPROACHES AND UNDISCOVERED POSSIBILITIES

Partner: PRSC

Place: Naujamiestis (Lithuania)

Date: 8/03/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The purpose of the conference was to review the actualities of the implementation of the principle of inclusion, to get acquainted with the possibilities of applying innovative strategies; to share experiences about the successes and proven practices of inclusive education, the ideas and possibilities of the project Let's care. The conference was addressed to teachers of the 1-8 grades, educational support specialists, University lecturers.

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

There have been presented 3 speeches about LET'S CARE: "Inclusive education - problems or opportunities?", "Guidelines for children's self-expression: play style and educator's position", "Environment as a third educator: practices of creating contexts".

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Networking contacts, new stakeholders involved

THE DIRECTION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION - TO REPLACE THE IMPOSSIBLE WITH THE POSSIBLE?

Partner: PRSC

Place: Panevezys (Lithuania)

Date: 28/08/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The objectives of the conference were to review the state of education in the municipality, to discuss the directions and challenges of the upcoming academic year, dissemination of international projects in the field of education carried out in the municipality

Among the participants there were several policy makers: the Mayor of Panevėžys District Municipality, Members of the Seimas of the Republic of Lithuania, the Vice Mayor of Panevėžys District Municipality, Members of the Committee on Education, Culture, Youth and Self-Government Affairs of the Municipal Council, Director of the Municipality Administration, Head specialists of the Department of Education, Culture and Sports, directors, and deputy directors for education of educational institutions, chairmen of methodological groups.

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

The direction of inclusive education in Lithuania - to replace the impossible with the possible?

How many steps from a failure to a success story?

Challenges and successes of implementation of the principles of inclusive education at school: the experience of the Velzys Gymnasium.

Activities of the project "LET'S CARE: let's create safe and successful schools that promote inclusive learning and improve educational achievements" in Lithuania.

5º CICLO DE CONFERÊNCIAS: INOVAR EM EDUCAÇÃO

Partner: UCP

Place: **Viseu (Portugal)**

Date: **6-13/01/2024**

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The work of the conference took place in 8 sectional sessions, in which more than 100 researchers. This was a conference in Viseu (Portugal) for teachers at the schools in that region focused on innovation in education. LET'S CARE was invited by one of the organizing schools to share the project (this school is part of the CoS in Portugal for LET'S CARE).

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://visprof.cfae.pt/formacao/turma/229/detalhe/>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

LET'S CARE project was presented to the teachers along with the initial results from the systematic literature review conducted by UCP within the LET'S CARE project.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

This participation was intended to sensitize teachers (about 250) from this region to the fieldwork that will be conducted within the LET'S CARE project.

LINK TO THE AGENDA:

https://visprof.cfae.pt/media/visprof/acao/238/anexos/web-programa_5-ciclo-de-conferencias_inovar-educacao_cidadania-e-trabalho-em-rede_2023_Qufb8Go.pdf

45TH ANNUAL CONFERENCE OF THE INTERNATIONAL SCHOOL PSYCHOLOGY ASSOCIATION (ISPA)

Partner: UCP

Place: Riga (Latvia)

Date: 3-6/07/2024

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

This is an annual conference organised by the International School Psychology Association. It is a renowned conference in the area of educational and school psychology, particularly due to the presence of multiple researchers and practitioners from all over the world. LET'S CARE project focuses on the school setting and its results have implications for the work of school and educational psychologists, as well as of other stakeholders of the school setting. Therefore, this was thought to be a good event for us to participate in.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

[ISPA 2024 | \(ispaweb.org\)](https://ispaweb.org)

[ISPA 2024 SimpleAbstracts 06.07.2024-1.pdf \(ispaweb.org\)](#)

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

The Portuguese LET'S CARE team presented results from data with teachers and parents on facilitators and barriers to safe teaching. Results showed that teachers' relationship strategies facilitate the development of safe teaching: knowing students, showing concern for students and being a safe haven for students. Pedagogical strategies such as tailoring strategies to each student/class were also mentioned as facilitators. Likewise, parents mentioned teaching strategies which facilitate safe teaching, mainly the use of positive encouragement and reinforcement and teachers' dedication to create a relationship with students. On the other hand, teachers' lack of time to build relationships with students, their bureaucratic load and low well-being were pointed out as barriers to safe teaching. One main conclusion is that both teachers and parents agreed that the teacher-student's bond is very important but must be intentionally developed.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

There were two main results with this participation: a) thought-provoking reflection within the research team and together with participants about the implications for the practice of school and educational psychologists from the results of the presented study; b) dissemination of the LET'S CARE project and its online platforms to an international audience.

Annex 6 – Results of the dissemination activities - Knowledge

NUMBER OF KNOWLEDGE EVENTS

Table 16 - Number of knowledge events per partner

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Training events	11		6	2	1		19	63	1	12		3		118
TOTAL	11	0	6	2	1	0	19	63	1	12	0	3	0	118

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER KNOWLEDGE EVENT PER PARTNER

Table 17 - Number of participants per Knowledge event per partner

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Training events	6,262		680	60	6		1,373	10,150	30	583		202		19,346
TOTAL	6,262	0	680	60	6	0	1,373	10,150	30	583	0	202	0	19,346

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER TARGET GROUP REACHED IN KNOWLEDGE EVENTS PER PARTNER

Table 18 - Number of participants per target groups reached

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PRO MA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Students	80				5		192							277
Families	6,182						26	201				32		6,441
Education Scientific Community							23	5				10		38
Teachers			356	42	1		453	6,099	30	568		156		7,705
Schools			324	18			105					4		451
Policy Makers & Authorities							55	2		15				72
NGOs & Advocacy Organisations							2							2
General Public							6							6
Asynchronous learners							511	3,843						4,354
TOTAL	6,262	0	680	60	6	0	1,373	10,150	30	583	0	202	0	19,346

Number of participants per target groups reached

Figure 17. – Number of participants per target groups reached

NUMBER OF KNOWLEDGE EVENTS PER GEOGRAPHICAL IMPACT

Table 19 - Number of knowledge events per geographical impact

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
European			3											3
National	5		3	1			4	63		6				82
Regional / Local	6			1	1		15		1	6		3		33
TOTAL	11	0	6	2	1	0	19	63	1	12	0	3	0	118

Number of knowledge events per geographical impact

Figure 18. – Number of knowledge events per geographical impact

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER GEOGRAPHICAL IMPACT AND PER PARTNER

Table 20 - Number of participants per geographical impact and per partner

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
European			427											427
National	6,182		253	36			734	10,150		360				17,715
Regional / Local	80			24	6		639		30	223		202		1,204
TOTAL	6,262	0	680	60	6	0	1,373	10,150	30	583	0	202	0	19,346

Number of participants per geographical impact

Figure 19. Number of participants per geographical impact